

The future of archives: Blockchain technology in the archival space

Anna Valenti

Student number: 13530232

Tutor: Michael Karabinos

Archives, Information and Society

Wordcount: 3895

Introduction

As archival digitalization remains a contested issue in the field of archives, technological innovations keep pushing for more accessible and transparent preservation practices. Raising from its almost entirely financial origins, Blockchain technology represents the latest novelty in archival science (Woodall and Ringel 2019). Recently taking over several non-economic spheres, decentralization and cryptography are being adopted for their public and democratic layout, particularly for infallible record-keeping matters (Lustig 2019). The nature of Blockchain, an immutable, distributed, public ledger, in which there is no party to trust - apart from the machine itself - makes it a perfect fit for enthusiasts' scenarios about an automated, flawless future in which the collection and distribution of information is entrusted to technology (Lustig 2019).

This trend of imagining Blockchain as a universal solution to all the problems pressed its adoption also in the archive field (Wijaksono et al. 2022). Archival science was already adapting to the re-invented concepts of documenting and collecting brought by digitalization, pursuing more openness and better interactivity and preservation. However, the integration of a distributed structure in which no hierarchy is defined, permissionless, with an impeccable memory, and in which no institution or third-party has any say in the matter (Dodd 2018), would inevitably affect archival practices and what archive means per se.

The aim of this study is investigating the different ways in which the traditional definition of archives fits in the implementation of Blockchain technology in archival studies and to what extent this technology represents a tool for better archival practices. The paper develops as follows: in the first section, I introduce the traditional definition of archives, addressing the three archival principles according to Theimer (2012), the meaning of record and narrative and the four periods of history silencing by Trouillot (1995). Subsequently, I give a general definition of Blockchain and the imaginary of a Blockchain 3.0, and the introduction of smart contracts. Afterwards, I present my method section and contextualize my analysis. In the final part of the paper, I discuss whether Blockchain in the archival future symbolizes an opportunity for better preservation or rather a threat to the original vision of archives.

While academic debate around archival digitalization is in general extensive (Theimer 2012, Acker and Brubaker 2014, Lane and Hill 2010), it often emphasizes the discussion around social media archives and born-digital archives. What is remarkable, instead, is the lack of analysis of more cutting-edge technologies (like Blockchain) that would completely revolutionize the field. This paper addresses this gap, making sense of the actual future perspectives of archives in a world in which machines are believed (or desired) to become future leaders (Lustig 2019).

I argue that, even if the future of archives may lie in Blockchain technology, its application in the specific case of archival science may bring several risks both in terms of algorithmic discrimination and inaccurate history narration. Moreover, the implementation of such system would inevitably change the very nature of archives, turning them into automated information machines in which emotion-less narratives are thrown without contextualization.

Theoretical background

1. Into the archival field

In the following section, I present the most traditional definition of archives as they are understood in archival study. Addressing Trouillot's four periods of history silencing (1995), I subsequently explore the processes of stories and silences' creation in archives.

1.1 Archives in the tradition

The most original definition of archives is provided by the Society of American Archivists as:

Materials created or received by a person, family, or organization, public or private, in the conduct of their affairs and preserved because of the enduring value contained in the information they contain or as evidence of the functions and responsibilities of their creator, especially those materials maintained using the principles of provenance, original order, and collective control. (2005)

As Theimer (2012) puts it, the idea of archives that emerges from this conceptualization is that of a repository and not that of a mere "collection" for specific purposes, as instead it is now envisioned in digital humanities (Theimer 2012). Selecting the

material that is worth archiving is defined as *appraisal* and the aggregation of the records is operated according to an organic relationship between them (Theimer 2012). The main purpose of the archival processes is to store information about the past. The International Council of Archives defines them as witnesses of the past, describing previous and present events and therefore changing and being changed by society in a recursive loop (2016).

When I mention the “material” aggregated during appraisal, I refer to archival documents or records, understood by Ketelaar as “a persistent representation of activities and transactions” (2019, 18). The authenticity of these records is fundamental in archival studies and is generally provided through internal (i.e., physical characteristics, content, and structure) and external (i.e., context) evidence (Theimer 2012). Context is also fundamental to the archival document, as it reduces the risks of misinterpretation of the archive (Whaanga 2015).

As stated in the definition of archives, records are kept according to the three principles of: provenance, original order, and collective control. Theimer (2012) defines provenance as “the history of an object, its creation and ownership”. The provenance of records also imposes their original order, which should be reproduced in the archival process (Theimer 2012). Applying the principle of collective control, finally, means understanding who created the record and for whom (Theimer 2012). Further in the paper, it will be assessed how these principles apply to the Blockchain technology in the archival world.

1.2 Stories and silences

Every archive makes up a narrative thanks to the totality of the stories embedded in every record and to the way they are selected and organized (Notari 2021). However, drawing from Harris’ (2021) definition of archives as a “sliver of a window into the event” (64), narratives are not representative of history itself; they can be constructed, misinterpreted, or kept secret. Silences are common in history production, and Trouillot (1995) identifies four moments in history in which past is silenced. They are: fact-creation (no registration of records), fact-assembly (as we do not keep every record), fact-retrieval (how narratives are created), and retrospective significance (when history is created) (Trouillot 1995). As master narratives and silenced ones are fundamental aspects of archives, it is relevant to this analysis assessing how narratives are exposed or furthermore hidden within a Blockchain-based archival system.

2. Blockchain

This section provides an overview of the Blockchain technology and its structure. Afterwards, it explores the future applications of the technology in non-financial contexts.

2.1 A distributed, public, immutable ledger

Blockchain technology was introduced to the public in 2009 as the underlying infrastructure of Bitcoin (De Filippi and Hassan 2016). It is defined as “a decentralized, secure and incorruptible database (or public ledger) that constitutes the foundational tool for peer-to-peer value creation and trustless transactions” (De Filippi and Hassan 2016). It is a system that sends value from place to place, verifying and identifying it through hashes (i.e., cryptographic signatures) within a network of blocks and nodes (i.e., users). The Blockchain is furthermore defined as distributed and decentralized, due to the absence of a central node or authority: the recording of every transaction is distributed to all the nodes in the network, which are independent (De Filippi and Hassan 2016). As mentioned, the Blockchain keeps record of every transaction, and as it was born to be a democratic, transparent technology, the recording of all these transactions is publicly available. Since Blockchain technology builds also on its anonymity (Swartz 2016), only the wallet numbers that execute the transactions are public. Due to its decentralized blocks structure, the code of the Blockchain is immutable. The chain can still be forked through consensus protocols, but transactions cannot be restored (Lustig 2019).

2.2 Blockchain 3.0 and future imaginaries – smart contracts in non-economic contexts

Even though Blockchain was introduced as the technology allowing online payments to be executed, imaginaries and projects around its possible non-economical uses abound. As one of the future waves of Blockchain technology, Swan (2015) identifies Blockchain 3.0 as the structure that will use Blockchain technology to “articulate decentralized principles of government and justice”.

Blockchain’s characteristics allow its employment in various fields, in which coins and financial transactions are not necessarily the central issue. Its main application outside of economics is that of record-keeping activities due to its distributed, immutable memory. The recent development of smart contracts (namely, small snippets of code uploaded on the Blockchain, executed if certain conditions are met) (De Filippi and Hassan 2016), widens

even more the spectrum of opportunities provided by this technology: health, education, politics (Kamath 2018). Since Blockchain technology is being implemented in an increasing number of fields, its record-keeping power represents an interesting prospect for digital preservation in the archival field (Woodall and Ringel 2019).

Method

The analysis conducted in this paper investigates the opportunities and threats represented by the implementation of a Blockchain-based archival system. Building on the abovementioned definition of archives and Blockchain, it moves further into their entanglement and disparities. My analysis is primarily interpretative: I use the very foundational concepts of archives to study whether they still fit into a Blockchain archival discourse, or whether the latter represents a record-keeping process that is now entirely detached from the archival discipline.

My analysis also takes into consideration some Blockchain-based archival projects so to study the effective application of this technology in the archival field and what steps were already taken to pursue it.

ARCHAIN. ARCHAIN is a Blockchain based archival system, developed in Russia for the State archive-keeping committee and extensively analysed by Galiev et al. (2019).

The UK Land registry. A registration system for land ownership developed in the United Kingdom based on a distributed ledger technology (Wijaksono et al. 2022).

Blockcert. A tool created by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology to “create, issue and verify Blockchain-based certificates” (Wijaksono et al. 2022, 67).

These projects employ Blockchain for more secure and accurate information storing practices. Verification processes are done by a mathematical process in the Blockchain network, which also assess ownership and authenticity (Wijaksono et al. 2022). Every transaction is stored and registered on the Blockchain, which manages the records almost entirely (Wijaksono et al. 2022).

My research identifies several patterns that suggest a promising future of the archival discipline within Blockchain technologies, but also several frictions between the two spheres.

Accordingly, my findings consist in a collection of specific areas in which frictions between the traditional archival discourse and the Blockchain technological perspectives emerge.

Analysis

The analysis conducted in this paper focuses on four different elements that are significant to the examination of a possible Blockchain-based archives future scenario and the current projects. Hence, the sections' subject matters are the following: 1) definitions and principles, 2) structure, 3) silences and narratives, 4) archivists and algorithms.

1. The three archival principles in the Blockchain and appraisal

As the traditional definition of archives states, materials are collected for the enduring value of the information they preserve (Society of American Archivists 2005). This definition already suggests some concerns regarding the storing of material on the Blockchain: how can a technology - which is known as a “trustless” system - assess the value of the material, and how can it pursue the process of appraisal in a critical way? Since the traditional definition of archives is not that of a collection of materials chosen for their purpose but their significance, it seems that a Blockchain archival system could shift the meaning of archives towards a more digital humanist perspective. Moreover, the concept of record itself is considerably reinterpreted within Blockchain technology, as records are treated as transactions, and they are not kept entirely, since Blockchain only stores hashes of the records (Wijaksono et al. 2022). The lack of direct accessibility to the record, which becomes an encrypted code in a network, dramatically alters its nature as it is conceived in the archival field. As Williams and Jones (2017) say in their explanation of ARCHAIN, encrypted files would be accessible only with a description key, otherwise, records would be visible in the Blockchain as a cryptographic signature (i.e., a series of numbers).

Because archives build also on the three principles that drive the appraisal and categorization of records, it is interesting to study whether Blockchain improves or complicates the application of these principles. Due to the infallible memory of Blockchain technology and the impossibility of modifying data, I claim that assessing provenance and defining original order in the Blockchain would be easier. Indeed, thanks to timestamping, it

would be possible to trace the custodial history of a record back to its very beginning, and at the same time also verifying the donor's identity while respecting their anonymity (Wijaksono et al. 2020).

The potential of Blockchain in assessing ownership is employed in the UK Land Registry and Blockcert projects, whose function is precisely that of verifying certificates and properties in an error-less environment (Wijaksono et al. 2020).

However, applying collective control would be more challenging in the Blockchain, as it would be impossible for the algorithms to critically understand why a record was created, and for whom.

2. Structure gap: Hierarchy vs distributed ledger on a horizontal axis.

There is a fundamental structural gap between traditional archives and Blockchain-based archives, which automatically also influences the conservation of the records. Indeed, as stated by Zhang (2012), archival arrangement of record is organized on five levels, which creates an ideal hierarchical order: “depository, record group, series, filing unit, and document” (334). This structure is functional and logical and indicates the organic relationship between records. Blockchain technology is instead known for its decentralized and distributed structure, purposefully opposing every centralized or hierarchical organization. In Blockchain-based systems, there is no central authority which has more power or importance than other nodes, but every node is part of a distributed network on a horizontal axis in which the information is retained equally (Lustig 2019).

Here, a re-imagination of the organization of traditional archives themselves is necessary, even though this condition not necessarily represents a threat to archivalization. For example, the ARCHAIN archival structure of blockwaves ensures that every miner in the network has a copy of all the transactions, both before and after they joined the network (William and Jones 2017). This happens without any type of hierarchization, but in the form of “lists” (William and Jones 2017, 8). In this way, information is not held and distributed through a central institution, which would make the material vulnerable to manipulation, but by all the nodes in the ledger that verifies the data through a consensus mechanism (William and Jones 2017).

3. Uncovering history silences through the Blockchain: what will be of narratives?

Traditional archives have, often throughout history, been accused of silencing or misrepresenting narratives (Bastian 2013). However, as Bastian (2013) points out, thanks to technology “we can imagine seamless, intertwined, and layered stories that accept and accommodate the complexities and contrariness of human expressions, accounts that locate minor and master narratives on interactive planes, and chronicles that privilege cultural values” (129). Talking about Blockchain’s potential outside of the financial sphere, Dodd (2018) claims that its implementation for record-keeping and information storing practices could “stop us from lying to history” (50). This idea of the Blockchain as a transparent and infallible system that prevents the burying of stories and narratives answers the concerns of history silencing theorized by Trouillot (1995).

Blockchain’s supporters state that, thanks to Blockchain itself, new record-keeping systems can have one-to-one correspondence to reality, storing uncorrupted information, which is verified through the network without the intervention of any third party (Dodd 2018). Such a scenario would avoid distortions in fact-creation (through timestamped evidence uploaded on the Blockchain) and fact-assembly (thanks to the infallible memory of the ledger) (Dodd 2018). However, I claim that problems would emerge in the representation of narratives in the Blockchain.

As stated above, records on the ledger are represented as hashes, viz a sequence of numbers. When the identity of a record becomes a mathematical formula in a distributed network, how can we still talk about narratives? On the Blockchain, no stories are told, neither master, nor alternative. The structure of the system itself prevents the creation of a history and a context around the document, which places its authenticity at risk (Wijaksono et al. 2020).

4. The disappearance of archivists: will algorithms take over archives?

The discussion around Blockchain-based archival systems pushes aside the role of the archivist, who becomes a phantom presence in the archival process. While Postmodernism gave the archivist the new role of narrator of records (Lane and Hill 2010), the recent debate about the use of Blockchain technology for information-keeping practices seems to bring back the Jekinsonian archivist: a passive, invisible individual who does not have any agency

on the material (Lane and Hill 2010). The process of appraisal and the organization of records are handed over to the machine, which automatically stores information into the blocks.

ARCHAIN project again provides an example of the shift to this almost entirely technological-driven system, in which archivists disappear. As stated in the explanation of how data is archived on the Blockchain of ARCHAIN by Williams and Jones (2017), users would perform “unverified archiving – storing data on the weave without external supervision” (14). This means that information would be stored in an arbitrary way, being verified through consensus protocols in the network (Williams and Jones 2017). While this procedure might seem desirable due to the impossibility of data being modified or corrupted by an external party, it is important to underline the consequences of an archive in which no selection is carried out, and in which validity is assessed through protocols.

As Woodall and Ringel (2019) highlight, Blockchain archival discourse addresses the problem of trustworthiness of records, and promises large archival storage, however it “obscures the role of human labor in archival imaginaries” (2210). The algorithms and the machine take over the work of the archivist, operating autonomously and eclipsing the human from the archival process (Woodall and Ringel 2019). This idea of an independent system that works for the human recalls the sociotechnical imaginaries of autonomous system of the Blockchain community studied by Lustig (2019). In these imaginaries, autonomous technologies fade into the background working seamlessly for the human, becoming artificial managers, and pursuing menial tasks while people can carry out more important activities to them (Lustig 2019). In particular, the idea of artificial managers that do all the work matches well with the idea of a Blockchain-based archival system, in which the human just uploads the record on the ledger, while the technology takes care of verifying it, storing it, and keeping it for the future.

Discussion

The implementation of the Blockchain in the archival field depicts a future trustless, automated archive, that circumvents the intervention and influence of third parties. Just like with Bitcoin in 2009, Blockchain represents a way out the decades of governmental and institutional control over archives (Bastian 2013). As Berger (2013) points out, archives have

always been part of bigger national state-centric projects to promote master narratives, putting politics above trustfulness. Mbembe (2002) describes the archive as a talisman, a mere mean to the end of abolishing the state's debt and commodifying memory. However, the unmediated nature of Blockchain technology, on which no state nor organization establishes rules nor operates censorship, might be the solution to the centenary reputation of archives as corrupted governmental tools. The ARCHAIN project, similarly to the Blockcert and the UK Land project, indeed aims at "putting the archive beyond the reach of censorship" (Williams and Jones 2017, 1).

Williams and Jones (2017) state that ARCHAIN addresses two other problems of the traditional archival system: the corruption of documents and the lack of accessibility. While wider accessibility is surely profitable, and the history of the Internet has already proved its potential in granting "improved access to information" (Williams and Jones 2017, 2), the issues of incorruptibility should be further addressed. As De Filippi and Hassan (2016) claim in discussing the application of smart contracts to law, the problem with Blockchain technology is that it is immutable. While this fixture certainly avoids the distortion of information by external parties, it also prevents any adjustment of the code in case it is wrong, no longer applicable or desired (De Filippi and Hassan 2016). This means that, if there is any mistake in the material, in its storing or in the way information itself is presented, it cannot be solved in any way. Returning to the issue of narratives discussed above, I claim that a narrative is still present in the Blockchain-based archival system: that of the machine.

As archiving becomes more and more a responsibility of the code (and not the human) concerns of algorithmic discrimination and digital noise rise. Due to the increasing employment of machine learning technique in the programming of algorithms, the human behind the process disappears more and more. In the desperate attempt of saving history, putting it into the hands of technology, we are risking of burying it, making it emotion-less, a collection of numbers and code in the realm of the immaterial.

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to research what characteristics of traditional archives a Blockchain-based archival system could retain, and whether this new system improves or complicates even further archival practices. Through the support of the cases study of

ARCHAIN, Blockcert, and the UK Land Registry, I put apart the traditional definition of archives and records, their structure and narrative power, and the role of the archivist, to analyze what is left of these elements in the Blockchain archival discourse. What emerges from my findings is a future scenario in which the record-keeping process is in some respects enhanced, in others even more intricate and biased. While a Blockchain archive ensures more accessibility and a more democratic structure in which every document has the same relevance and no third party intervenes (Williams and Jones 2017), other aspects which are fundamental to an accurate history narration are put at stake, such as the preservation of the original form of the record (Woodall and Ringel 2019).

Even if the future of archives surely lies in cutting-edge technologies (e.g., Blockchain), the implementation of these systems in the archival field subverts the very meaning of archives and their practices. Therefore, I conclude that, as for the cases studies analyzed and in general the use of Blockchain to regulate information-storing processes, we cannot anymore refer to archives and archiving in their most essential understanding.

This research focused on a comparative interpretation of the most cardinal concepts of the archival field and their potential application in the Blockchain archival discourse. The focus on three cases study and the lack of more technical information about the matter surely represents a limitation for this study. Future research could further investigate a wider range of Blockchain-based projects for archiving and dig deeper into the very functioning of the infrastructure, to better understand the destiny of records once they are uploaded on the ledger. Also, an examination should be conducted over the environmental impact of Blockchain-based archives, due to the concerns around the high usage of carbon of Blockchain technology that have been raised recently (Juarez 2021). Moreover, it would be interesting to study what is left of the original idea of Blockchain in new systems of blockwaves, like the ARCHAIN one, studying for examples what is the role of tokens in these environments.

Bibliography

Acker, Amelia, and Jed Brubaker. 2014. "Death, Memorialization, and Social Media: A Platform Perspective for Personal Archives." *Archivaria* 77 (May), 1-23.

- Bastian, Jeannette. 2013. "The records of memory, the archives of identity: celebrations, texts, and archival sensibilities." *Archival Science* 13, 121-131.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10502-012-9184-3>
- Berger, Stefan. 2013. "The role of national archives in constructing national master narratives in Europe." *Archival Science* 13, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10502-012-9188-z>
- De Filippi, Primavera, and Samer Hassan. 2016. "Blockchain Technology as a Regulatory Technology: From Code is Law to Law is Code." *First Monday* 21 (12).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5210/fm.v21i12.7113>
- Dimas Wijaksono, Satrio, Ramadhan Hadi Trianto, and Awal Febri Ikhtiarman. 2022. "Execution of Blockchain in The World of Archive." *Blockchain Frontier Technology* 2 (1):64-71. <https://doi.org/10.34306/bfront.v2i1.115>
- Dodd, Nigel. 2018. "The Social Life of Bitcoin." *Theory, Culture & Society*, 35(3): 35–56.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/026327641774646>
- Galiev, Albert, Nikolai Prokopyev, Shamil Ishmukhametov, Evgeni Stolov, Rustam Latypov, and Ilya Vlasov. 2018. "Archain: A novel Blockchain based archival system." In *2018 Second World Conference on Smart Trends in Systems, Security and Sustainability (WorldS4)*, 84-89. <https://doi.org/10.1109/WorldS4.2018.8611607>
- Harris, Verne. 2002. "The archival sliver: Power, memory, and archives in South Africa." *Archival Science* 2, 63–86. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02435631>
- International council on Archives. 2016. "Why Archiving?" Available from <https://www.ica.org/en/why-archiving> (Accessed 9 December 2022).
- Juarez, Geraldine. 2021. "The Ghostchain." *Paletten Nr. 325*. Available from <https://paletten.net/artiklar/the-ghostchain> (Accessed 15 December 2022).

- Kamath, Reshma. 2018. "Blockchain for Women Next Generation for Sustainable Development Goal 5." *Asian Development Perspectives*.
<https://doi.org/10.22681/ADP.2018.9.1.88>
- Ketelaar, Eric. 2020. *Archiving People : a Social History of Dutch Archives*. Gravenhage: Stichting Archiefpublicaties.
- Lane, Victoria ,and Jennie Hill. 2010. "Where do we come from? What are we? Where are we going? Situating the archive and archivists." In *The future of archives and recordkeeping: A reader*, 3-22. 2010.
- Lustig, Caitlin. 2019. "Intersecting Imaginaries: Visions of Decentralized Autonomous Systems." *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 3 (CSCW): 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3359312>
- Mbembe, Achille. 2002. "The Power Of The Archive And Its Limits". In *Refiguring The Archive*, 19—26. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Notari, Federica. 2021. "The Living Archive." *Collecting Otherwise*. Available from <https://collectingotherwise.hetnieuweinstituut.nl/en/essay-living-archive> (Accessed 23 October 2022).
- Peace-Moses, Richard. 2005. "Archives." in *A Glossary of Archives and Records Terminology* Chicago: Society of American Archivists. Available from http://www.archivists.org/glossary/term_details.asp?DefinitionKey=156 (Accessed 27 November 2022).
- Swartz, Lana. 2018. "What was Bitcoin, what will it be? The techno-economic imaginaries of a new money technology." *Cultural Studies*, 623-650.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09502386.2017.1416420>
- Swan, Melanie. 2015. *Blockchain: Blueprint for a New Economy*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.

Theimer, Kate. 2012. "Archives in Context and as Context." *Journal of Digital Humanities* 1 (2)

Trouillot, Michel-Rolph. 1995. *Silencing the Past: Power and the Production of History*. Boston, MA: Beacon Press.

Whaanga, Hēmi, David Bainbridge, Michela Anderson, Korii Scrivener, Papitha Cader, Tom Roa and Te Taka Keegan. 2015. "He Matapihi Mā Mua, Mō Muri: The Ethics, Processes, and Procedures Associated with the Digitization of Indigenous Knowledge—The Pei Jones Collection." *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly*, 53(5-6): 520-547.

Williams, Sam, and Will Jones. 2017. "Archain: An Open, Irrevocable, Unforgeable and Uncensorable Archive for the Internet." Available from <https://www.arweave.org/whitepaper.pdf> (Accessed 10 December 2022).

Woodall, Angela, and Sharon Ringel. 2020. "Blockchain archival discourse: Trust and the imaginaries of digital preservation." *New Media & Society*, 22(12): 2200–2217. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444819888756>

Zhang, Jane. 2012. "Archival context, digital content, and the ethics of digital archival representation." *KO KNOWLEDGE ORGANIZATION* 39 (5), 332-339. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0943-7444-2012-5-332>